

CLASSIFICATION OF PREPOSITIONS IN ARABIC LANGUAGE

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Annotation: A large part of the group of auxiliary words is made up of words called prepositions. Since the number of agreements in Arabic is very small, the subject, relation of events to time, place, delimitation and other various relations are mainly expressed using prepositions.

Key words: Arabic grammar, meaningful adverbs, preposition, agreement, vocabulary.

Introduction

A common feature of prepositions is that they come before the word to which they are attached and force that word to appear in the accusative case.

For example: في --- ... at في مدرسة --- at school,
إلى --- ... to إلى الكلية --- to faculty,
من --- ... from من الرجلين --- from two men.

Data collection and analysis

Prepositions are divided into three groups according to their structure:

I. Original prepositions. Words that have lost their independent word form and are used only as prepositions are original prepositions. Original prepositions include:

1. في --- ... in (below, only the main meaning of the prepositions will be given. To find out other meanings, it is necessary to refer to existing dictionaries).
في المعهد --- in Institute. في predlog ... in with this menaing is not used for people.

2. إلى --- ... to, ... till (until). إلى المساء --- until the evening.

3. من --- ... from. من الصباح from morning.
4. علي --- ... on. علي الطاولة on the table.
5. عن --- ... haqida. عن الدرس dars haqida.
6. ب --- with, by. بالقلم - with pen.
7. لدي --- ...in the presence. لدي الأستاذ - in the presence of the teacher
8. مع --- with together. مع الصديق - with friend together.
9. ل --- ...of, have/has. للطالب - student has.
10. ك --- as, like. كالشمس - like sun.
11. حتي --- ...until. حتي الصباح until morning.
12. منذ --- ...since منذ سنتين - since two years.

II. Noun-prepositions. This group includes words that have not lost their noun character, can be used as a noun, but at the same time can also act as a preposition. When these are used as prepositions, they often come in the accusative case:

1. داخل - in, into. داخل المدرسة - in school.
2. خارج - out, out of. خارج البيت - out of house.
3. عبر - through. عبر الهواء - through the air.
4. خلال - during. خلال العطلة - during the holiday.
5. بين - between. بين التلميذين - between two students.
6. قرب - near. قرب النافذة - near to window.
7. أمام - front of. أمام الوالدين - front of parents.
8. إزاء - opposite. إزاء النافورة - opposite of the fountain.
9. وراء - behind. وراء الجدار - behind to door.
10. فوق - on. فوق الماء - on water.
11. تحت - under. تحت الشجرة - under tree
12. خلف - back side. خلف فاطمة - Back side of Fotima.
13. عند - ... in the presence of عند المدير - in the presence of the chief.

14. حول – around. حول المسألة – around the topic.
15. حوالى – about. حوالى متر – about a meter.
16. قبل - ...before. قبل الظهر – before noon.
17. بعد - ...after. بعد الدرس – after lesson.
18. أثناء – during. أثناء الزيارة – during the visit.
19. ضد - ...against to. ضد العدوان – against to aggression.
1. نجاه –oppisite. نجاه النافورة – opposite the fountain.
2. تلو - ...follow. تلو الأباء – to follow the fathers
3. إبان – during. إبان الحرب – during the war.

These words can sometimes take other prepositions as independent words:

إلى الأمام – forward.

من وراء – behind.

III. Complex prepositions, These consist of two or three words and express more complex relationships than the above pedlogs:

1. لأجل - ...for.
2. في سبيل - ...for.
3. خلافا ل - ...despite.
4. خوفا من - ...afraid of.
5. فضلا عن - ...out of.
6. على مقربة من – near to.
7. بالقرب من - near to, next to.
8. بجانب - near to.
9. بالرغم من - ...despite .
10. بصرف النظر عن – ... in addition to, regardless of
11. بالنظر إلى – reason of.
12. نظرا إلى – reason of.
13. عوضا عن - ... to the fraction of.
14. عوضا ل - ... to the fraction of.

15. نتیجتة ل - ... as a result of.
16. بواسطة - in this way
17. بجوار - at, near.
18. في غضون - ...during.

Among the above, prepositions ل، ب، ك --- and these prepositions are involved

Compound prepositions are written by adding the word after it.

For example:

بالريشة - with pero. كالسيف - like a sword.

ل - preposition ال when added to words with the article of certainty, the hyphen in the article is omitted in writing. For example:

ل - for judgment. = ل + الحكم

ل When the prefix

ل is added to the words starting with the letter, ل the letter l is written one and can be read in two ways.

For example:

للبن = ل + اللبن : للبن = ل + اللبن

All other prepositions are written separately from the word after it.

Result and disvussion

Prepositions mainly come in front of the words of the noun group and enter into a relationship with them, but they can also affect some verbs. This or that verb can have different meanings depending on the preposition that follows it¹.

1. Egyptian philologist Muhammad Makkawi writes in his book "Kitabum Mavadi'u (Hatta) fil Qur'an-il Karim" that Arabic grammar is characterized by the movement of the end of words. He also mentioned that words are divided into 3 parts: noun, verb and letter. He

¹ Ibrohimov N., Yusupov M. "Arab tili grammatikasi" 1, Namangan-2009, b-111

said that there are 80 types of letters. He listed the 3 most popular types of letters in the Arabic language. Muhammad Makkawi in his book "Letters",

2. and divided them into 3 groups.
3. 1. Khuruful Mabani - Letters of the Alphabet (28)
4. 2. Meaningful meaning - letters that give meaning in a sentence (80)
5. 3. Khuruful alphabet - - these letters are used in the order of large sentences, and each letter has its own number (28).
- 6.
7. Khuruful is divided into 2 according to the structure of meaning, i.e. prepositions that give meaning:
8. 1. Khurufu as sabita - fixed prefixes (which do not change and do not change their place in texts)
9. 2. Khuruful mutagayyara - prefixes that change (prefixes that change depending on the change of the text in the text)
10. At the same time, the meaning of khuruful is divided into 2 according to the effect it has on the end of the words:
11. 1. Huruful Amila
12. 2. Huruful Atila
13. And the structure of prefixes is divided into 5 according to the number of components:
14. 1. Prefixes consisting of 1 letter
15. 2. Prefixes consisting of 2 letters
16. 3. Prefixes consisting of 3 letters
17. 4. Prefixes consisting of 4 letters
18. 5. Prefixes consisting of 5 letters

Only 1	2 letters	3 letters	4	5
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letter					letters	letters
13	26		25		15	1
الهمزة	أ	لن	أَيَّ	رُ بَّ	إِذَا	لَكِنَّ
الباء	إِذْ	لَوْ	أَجَلَ	سَدَّ وَفَّ	أَلَّا	
الكاف	أَلْ	لَا	إِذْنِ =إِذَا	عَدَا	إِلَّا	
التاء	أَمَّ	مِذَّ	إِذَا	عَدَا نَّ	أَمَّا	
النون	أَنَّ	مِنْ	أَلَّا	عَدَا لِي	إِمَّا	
الياء	إِنَّ	مَا	إِلَى	لَا تَا	حَتَّى	
الفاء	أَوْ	نَّ	أَمَّا	لِيَا تَا	حَاشَا	
اللام	أَيَّ	هَلْ	إِنَّ	مِذَّ نَا	كَأَنَّ	
الواو	بَلْ	هَا	أَنَّ	نَعَمَ م	كَلَّا	
السين	إِيَّ	وَا	أَيَّا	هَيَّا ا	لَعَلَّ	
الميم	عَنْ	يَا	بَلَى		لَكِنَّ	
الهاء	فِي		تَمَّ		لَمَّا	
الألف	قَدْ		جَلَلَّ		لَوْلَا	
	كِي		جِيرَ		لَوْمًا	
	لَمْ		خَلَا		هَلَّا	

Table 1.The list of prefixes in Arabic

So, as we mentioned above, we can see from the table that the number of prepositions that give meaning when they appear in a sentence is 80.

Conclusion

In conclusion, according to the effect they have on the nouns that come after them, that, the prefixes that cause the nouns to be different in agreement are divided into two:

1. Alhuruful-amila - prepositions that cause the end of words to appear in the accusative case, accusative case, silent case, and naskh case
2. Alhuruful-atila - prefixes that do not affect the end of words

References

1. Ibrohimov N.,Yusupov M. “Arab tili grammatikasi”
1,Namangan-2009,b-111
2. Muhammad makkaviy “Mufassal e’rob ”
3. <https://www.google.com/search?q=arab+tili+grammatikasida+kelishiklar&oq=arab+tili+grammatikasida+kelishiklar>
4. <https://alifarabic.com/what-are-the-prepositions-and-their-uses/#:~:text=Prepositions%20or%20as%20it%20is,understand%20where%20the%20book%20is.>